

TIV MARRIAGE SYSTEM BEFORE 1914

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Abstract: *This study examines the Tiv marriage system before 1914 as a central socio-cultural institution deeply embedded in the people’s lineage-based organization, religious worldview, and economic life. It analyses the decentralized nature of pre-colonial Tiv society and demonstrates how marriage functioned beyond a personal union to serve as a mechanism for lineage continuity, alliance formation, social regulation, and spiritual balance. The work explores the evolution and conduct of major traditional marriage forms including exchange marriage (yamshe), marriage by capture (iye), kem (bridewealth) marriage, companionship unions, marriage by purchase, and elopement, highlighting their origins, processes, and social significance. It further underscores the role of elders, kinship networks, akombo rituals, and tsav in regulating marital relations and maintaining communal harmony. The study argues that Tiv marriage practices before colonial rule were systematic, adaptive, and reflective of a sophisticated indigenous social organization, contrary to earlier colonial misinterpretations.*

1.1 Introduction

Before the advent of British colonial rule in 1914, the Tiv marriage system was a deeply structured institution that reflected the people’s socio-cultural values, lineage-centered worldview, and spiritual cosmology. Marriage among the Tiv was primarily a communal affair rather than an individual choice, reflecting the collective nature of reproduction, alliance formation, and economic cooperation. The various forms of marriage—such as exchange marriage

(yamshe/kwase yamen sha ishe), marriage by capture (iye), companionship unions, kem marriage (bridewealth), marriage by purchase, and elopement (ii kwase); emerged from the Tiv’s decentralized socio-political setting and emphasized reciprocity between families and lineages.¹ These marriages reinforced the ideals of kinship solidarity, ensured continuity of lineage, regulated inheritance rights, and maintained the sacred order of ritual obligations associated with akombo and tsav. While later

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European writers often misunderstood these practices as “primitive,” indigenous accounts, such as Akiga Sai’s early ethnography demonstrate that

Tiv marriage customs were systematic, purposeful, and reflective of a sophisticated social organization.² In this chapter, the evolution of Tiv marriage system before official colonization of Tivland and subsequent social changes has been examined.

1.2 Socio-Cultural Organisation of the Tiv before the period of colonial rule.

It is safe to begin by establishing the fact that pre-1914 Tiv society operated under a highly decentralized social structure known as segmentary lineage organization, in which political authority was distributed horizontally rather than vertically. The Tiv lived in scattered homesteads clustered by extended families and agnatic lineages called ityo. This was bound together through descent from a common ancestor.³ Alfred Akawe Torkura provides an elaborate description of Tiv social-political organisation that it was segmented and was run by elders possessing Tsav. According to him, the compound (Ya), was the smallest unit of administration where heads of family units within a compound having the same father or grandfather, constitute a Council or Ya Council with the founder of the compound at the head.

He moved further to observe that the second level above Ya council or village council was what is known as Ye-Ingyor council which was made up of the compound heads which belong to the same great grandfather and who shared females for exchange marriage (this exchange marriage, we shall exhaustively discuss it later). The eldest among the compound heads invariably possessing Tsav, directs the affairs of this council. This inversed pyramidal arrangement runs through Tyo-council to Tar-Council, the latter being the highest in the territory.⁴ That is to simply say that Tiv did not have a central authority. This lack of centralized kingship distinguished the Tiv from their neighbouring peoples and influenced all aspects of social life, including marriage, conflict resolution, and ritual observances.⁵ This continued up until they began to borrow certain social-cultural practices from their neighbours like the Jukun, Idoma, Hausa, etc.

Furthermore, Akpenpuun Dzurgba explained that; the lineage (ityo) was the fundamental political and social unit in Tivland. Each lineage was composed of related households organized around a shared patrilineal ancestor whose descendants maintained ritual and economic ties. Members of an ityo participated jointly in rituals, inherited land collectively, and shared responsibility for marriage negotiations.

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Marriage therefore involved not only the bride and groom but the entire lineage group that mediated decisions, ensured compliance with customs, and protected collective interests.⁶ Corroborating this assertion, Thomas Igyah appreciates the manner in which Tiv perceived marriage. He notes that:

Marriage was seen beyond something that connected a man and woman but lineages or groups that were involved. When a man married from Ishangev for example, he has become one of the members of Ishangev people and the family he married from. It was a matter of pride to identify with certain groups or communities as the case may be that you married from them. The interest of the people you married from and their welfare and safety became your concern as a son-in-law and *visé vasa*.⁷

The Tiv were organized into larger territorial and descent groups called *tar*, which linked several lineages and clans into broader socio-cultural communities. These *tar* units formed the basis for larger ritual observances and inter-lineage cooperation, especially during crises such as famine, warfare, pestilence, and disputes over land or marital obligations. According to Torkula, the *tar* system reinforced unity and cultural identity by providing overarching norms

governing marriage, inheritance, and dispute resolution.⁸

Kinship played a central role in Tiv identity and social functioning. Kinship relations dictated obligations toward relatives, governed marriage eligibility, and provided the moral framework for cooperation. The Tiv strictly observed exogamy within the minimal lineage, meaning individuals could not marry those considered close kin. This rule shaped marriage alliances and ensured that marital unions served as bridges between separate families, reinforcing the network of inter-lineage reciprocity.⁹ Additionally, Torkula argues that, Marriage creates kinship in every society the world over. To him, marriage is a social institution that binds and holds society intact with the internally regulated mechanisms such as the prohibition of incest (*U-yaven-a-Tsombur*) and compliance with the rules of Endogamy and Exogamy.¹⁰

It may be significant to state that marriage among the Tiv was generally a group affair in which the man and the wife were mere arrowheads. The institution further created group alliance for stability and co-operation. Except sexual intercourse, the wife belonged to the entire family into which she was married, it was commonly said, *kwase-wase*, meaning “our wife”. She could cook, on demand for the

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husband's relations and the husband's relations would treat her respectfully as if they were her real husbands. Right in the family unit, kinship stated building up. Besides, among the Tiv, marriage pushed farther afield the boundary within which sexual and even marriage could be allowed. Marriage between the close blood relations of the wife and those of the husbands were not encouraged. This was because once the marriage was contracted, the husband's lineage became united into a kinship group with the wife's lineage which members concerned had to obey the regulations guiding the relationship. That was not all, even the children of the marriage became Anterev to the members of the father's group (Tyo), and their rights as members of the patrilinealism were fully accorded. Conversely, they became Angbiav to the relations of their mother.¹¹ This unity among the two groups was so much protected by the Tiv such that punishments were given to those who violated the traditional rules governing marriage system especially in terms of kinship. No wonder an informant note that:

Even among age grades (Mbakwav) it was forbidden that a man sleeps with his fellow orkwav (age mate). When it was noticed, the defaulter would be bitten and compelled to pay fine (wua tia) with a goat. It was done similarly when a brother and sister slept with each other;

also, it was forbidden to sleep with a mother-in-law be it direct or extended family.¹²

Recall that the household was the smallest functional unit of Tiv society, consisting of a polygynous male head, his wives, children, and dependent relatives. Each wife had her own hut and farm responsibilities, while the husband coordinated farming activities, security, and lineage obligations. The autonomy of wives within the compound varied, but marriage placed them within a system of rights, duties, and ritual expectations. Marriage thus formed part of the foundation of Tiv domestic and economic life.¹³

Tiv society was governed through councils of elders, who exercised authority based on age, spiritual power, and mastery of tradition. Elders mediated marriage exchanges, oversaw the negotiation of wards in exchange marriage, and performed vital rituals related to fertility, childbirth, and agricultural prosperity. Spiritual authority was tied to mastery of akombo (sacred forces) and tsav (mystical power), which further reinforced elder leadership in matrimonial matters.¹⁴

Religion permeated Tiv social organization, shaping moral norms and ritual obligations around marriage. Marriage was viewed as a sacred act that tied families together through spiritual and material bonds. Rituals associated

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with akombo governed the fertility of women, protection of offspring, and the harmony of households. Violations of marriage norms—such as improper exchanges or refusal to honor lineage obligations—were believed to attract spiritual consequences.¹⁵

Economic life in Tivland was based on agriculture, primarily the cultivation of yam, sorghum, millet, and other subsistence crops. Marriage played a strategic role in agricultural productivity because wives contributed significantly to food production. Through marriage alliances, families secured additional labor, expanded farmlands, and strengthened cooperative networks. Thus, marriage was both a socio-cultural and economic strategy essential for survival.¹⁶

Age grades (kwav/iyange) structured social responsibilities by grouping individuals according to age and gender. Young men formed communal labour teams responsible for farming, warfare, and communal projects, while elders provided leadership. Age grades also influenced courtship and marriage competition, as young men often showcased bravery and physical ability to attract marital partners or participate in rival companionship customs.¹⁷ There were instances where a member of the age grade communal labour team will lead his members to go and farm for his mother-in-law.

This created a platform for displaying brevity and getting wives as some were given wives in the process to appreciate the hero nature in them.

The Tiv maintained a rich oral tradition that transmitted knowledge across generations, including history, proverbs, laws, and marriage customs. Songs, stories, and rituals associated with marriage processes helped preserve moral values and regulated behavior within households. Rupert East's editing of Akiga's Story revealed the sophistication of Tiv oral culture and its role in structuring matrimonial norms and social expectations.¹⁸ It is in this wise that Dzurgba says; the Tiv worldview emphasized communalism rather than individualism. Every marriage, conflict, or ritual had implications for the lineage group, and individuals were expected to act in ways that promoted group cohesion. This worldview shaped the collective decision-making process in marriage arrangements and ensured that families maintained their dignity and social standing through adherence to customs.¹⁹

Apart from kinship and oral history, social harmony was maintained through customary law administered by elders and mediated through rituals. Since Tiv society lacked centralized authority, disputes—especially those related to marriage, infidelity, or bride

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disputes—were settled through local councils. These councils used marriage-related sanctions, compensation, and ritual cleansing to restore communal balance.²⁰ Based on the above, Tiv socio-cultural organization before 1914 was decentralized, lineage-based, and deeply embedded in a religious worldview; marriage served as the mechanism through which alliances were created, economic cooperation ensured, and spiritual obligations fulfilled. Understanding this structure is essential to grasping the evolution and complexity of Tiv traditional marriage systems.

1.3 The Evolution of Traditional Marriage System in Tivland

The evolution of Tiv marriage before 1914 was closely tied to the people's migration history and settlement patterns. Ethnographic evidence from Akiga Sai suggests that as the Tiv migrated southwards and settled in waves, marriage practices adapted to new social and environmental conditions. Early marriage systems were flexible and allowed families to form alliances essential for survival in unfamiliar territories.²¹

One of the earliest documented marriage systems was ingyor/ward marriage, in which girls were designated as wards to be given later in exchange. This system formed the basis of yamshe (exchange marriage), which later

became the dominant form. The development of exchange marriage was tied to the need for reliable inter-lineage cooperation during migration and settlement.²² According to Rupert East, Tiv did not have multiple forms of marriage as was later practiced. The only form of marriage was by exchange. For they would not allow the name of their child to be lost to their house for any cause except death. If a man had children he wanted all of them to remain his. So if, for instance, he had two sons and three daughters, he divided the daughters amongst the sons, to give in exchange for wives, who should bear children in the place of his own daughters who were with their children in the place of his own daughters who were with their husbands, that his house might expand and go forward.²³

Similarly, Torkula looking at the general aim of marriage among the Tiv opines that; the marriage was contracted mainly for the propagation of children to prolong and perpetuate the family lineage. According to him, the need for farm labour played a role in raising many children and by implication in most cases polygamous marriage became necessary. Meanwhile, of all the marriage institutions practiced among the Tiv, whether polygamous or monogamous marriage, exchange marriage was the most fundamental. Keep in mind that one of the features of exchange marriage that made it

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fascinating was the equalization which underlaid the cultural institution of marriage. Tiv society been an egalitarian society, the equalization system, was based on the equal number of off-springs by the exchange wife's welfare that not only did it guarantee but also remained the guiding principle, which ensured the stability of the marriage.²⁴ Also, another good thing about this system of marriage was that a daughter, which had to be married out of the family must have a replacement to take the place and propagate children to compensate for the daughter given out in marriage.²⁵

A woman married by exchange becomes a full member of the family, but a woman married in any other way is not so regarded. If a woman married by exchange should give birth in her father's house, the afterbirth will be taken home carefully and buried in the compound of her husband; whereas in the case of any other marriage it would be taken to her father's house, if she did not go home to her father to give birth. A woman married by exchange returning home is called "ive", i.e "as if" she no longer belongs to the family unless the contract is dissolved, an iverkwase is used as an igba in certain akombo.²⁶

In theory, exchange marriage is ideally simple. Every man takes his immediately younger sister as his marriage ward (ingol), gives her to another

man, who in return gives him his ward as wife. These two women called exchanged partners (ikar), then bear children of the same number and sex. On the deaths of the wives the matter is finished. In practice, complications arose at every step. One of the complications was in the acquisition of marriage wards. Children were not born in equal sex ratios in small groups not to talk of boy and girl alternatively. More so, some died of sicknesses or other occurrences. More challenges abound.²⁷

Subsequently, exchange marriage evolved into a complex socio-economic institution that regulated reproduction, inheritance, and ritual obligations. Over time, ward allocation no longer involved only full sisters but extended to broader kin groups to balance demographic constraints. This evolution was documented extensively by the Bohannans and earlier hinted at by Downes.²⁸ As population expanded and lineages multiplied, Tiv marriage evolved mechanisms to prevent inbreeding and ensure exogamy. Strict incest taboos were enforced to maintain lineage purity, and over time, marriage rules became more codified. Elders played an increasing role in regulating eligibility and ensuring compliance with cultural expectations.²⁹

Next, marriage by capture (iye) emerged during periods of inter-clan hostility and mobility. As

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Tiv settlements grew, some lineages established treaties permitting non-retaliatory capture between groups.³⁰ Therefore, closely related to exchange marriage was the iye marriage system. Marriage by capture, known as iye, emerged during periods of Tiv migration, warfare, and territorial expansion. As the Tiv encountered neighbouring groups, competition for women and alliance-building often produced contexts in which symbolic or actual capture became a recognized form of marriage.³¹ This implies an arrangement between two lineages, generally of adjoining utar, to allow the mutual capture of wives without revenge. Such treaties were made between fairly large lineages such as Ukum with Ugongo and Shitire respectively, while Ugondo with Ikurav. The treaty was validated by the death of a man or a dog, and sometimes some blood of those making the treaty was mixed with locust beans, salt, and palm oil and eaten. Where such a treaty was made, a man from group A might elope with a girl of group B without fear of her kinsmen's vengeance. Generally, someone was sent to inform her kinsmen of her whereabouts, and presents were made to the parents-in-law. At the birth of the first child, the wife's kinsmen came and tried to make arrangements to make an exchange marriage out

of the match; if such an exchange were not given, the children of that marriage were never secure in their father's ityo and would be considered as ishe ii ko unless an exchange was arranged.³² Over time, iye evolved into a recognized marriage form with its own rituals and pathways into exchange marriage.³³ The practice became a regulated system when lineages created "no-retaliation treaties," allowing young men to abduct women from agreed lineages without triggering conflict.³⁴ This institutionalization of capture marriage reflected both the Tiv warrior ethos and the flexibility of their social system, enabling unions to form even when families lacked wards for exchange.

Marriage by capture typically involved young men ambushing a woman during communal activities such as dances or market visits. The woman was taken to the man's home, where she would be protected by elders while negotiations proceeded.³⁵ Once the woman arrived, rituals were performed to prevent spiritual retaliation and to cleanse the act of abduction, invoking akombo spirits for protection.³⁶ The woman's family then visited either violently or peacefully to seek redress. Compensation—usually in livestock, brass rods, or future ward exchange—was required to legalize the union.³⁷ Once

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settled, the marriage was integrated into a recognized form, often later transforming into an exchange marriage.

Marriage by capture had certain advantages, including offering young men who lacked sisters or wards an opportunity to marry. It also elevated a man's social status, as successful capture demonstrated bravery and tactical ability.³⁸ Additionally, it ensured the redistribution of women across lineages, expanding sociopolitical networks. However, the system had notable challenges. It could provoke violence if treaties were violated or compensation refused. Women sometimes resisted the marriage, leading to instability in the household.³⁹ Moral concerns also grew over time, with elders condemning excessive violence or exploitation, prompting eventual decline before colonial rule intensified opposition.

Kem marriage later emerged as a parallel system to exchange marriage, developing as Tiv society grew wealthier through contact with Jukun, Hausa, and Udam traders. The introduction of brass rods, cattle, and cloth into Tiv economy made it increasingly possible for men to obtain wives through material payments rather than lineage exchanges.⁴⁰ Oral histories suggest kem was initially practiced by wealthier families or men without female wards, offering an inclusive

alternative that allowed more individuals to marry.⁴¹ Over time, kem gained legitimacy and spread across Tivland, though it remained secondary to exchange marriage prior to colonial regulation.

The kem process involved gradual payments of bridewealth from the groom's family to the bride's family. Payments were not required upfront; rather, they could span years, reflecting agricultural seasons and economic realities.⁴² Items included goats, chickens, brass rods, mats, cloth, and later money. Each installment conferred partial marital rights, but full rights—including claim over children—were secured only after completion of payments.⁴³ Ceremonies accompanied each phase, including blessings, feasting, and the symbolic escort of the bride to her new home. Elders mediated misunderstandings and ensured that obligations were honored.

The advantages of kem marriage included its flexibility and accessibility. It allowed men of varying economic backgrounds to marry and encouraged responsible labor to fulfill payments gradually.⁴⁴ Bridewealth also strengthened bonds between families and affirmed the value placed on women within the lineage. However, the system introduced challenges such as commercialization of marriage and potential

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exploitation through inflated demands. Incomplete payments could undermine the husband's authority or jeopardize children's lineage placement.⁴⁵ Furthermore, because rights were conditional, disputes often arose, especially when economic hardship prevented families from completing obligations.

The companionship marriage system, predominantly practiced in the Masev area of Tivland, emerged as a cultural adaptation to increased social competition among young men and the growing significance of youthful courtship relationships. Oral traditions captured by Akiga Sai show that companionship arose as young men sought avenues to express affection and emotional attachment outside the highly structured norms of exchange marriage.⁴⁶ These relationships served as informal romantic partnerships, allowing young women to form bonds prior to formal marriage negotiations. The system was partly a response to generational tensions: while elders retained strong control over marital arrangements, young people crafted companionship as a sphere of autonomy, thereby shaping precolonial Tiv social life in subtle yet important ways.⁴⁷

Companionship unions typically began at social gatherings such as moonlight dances, communal farming activities, festivals, or market events where young people interacted freely. Once a

young man and woman declared companionship, the relationship was recognized socially and included emotional loyalty, gift exchanges, and occasional sexual relations.⁴⁸ The most dramatic feature was the ritual known as "purging of akombo" performed when a married woman conceived her first child. Her former companion was required to bring gifts and participate in fertility rites that symbolically blessed the pregnancy, acknowledging both past intimacy and social rivalry with the husband. These rituals reduced potential conflict and integrated companionship into the broader moral order of Tiv society.⁴⁹ Elders sometimes disapproved, but society accepted the system as long as boundaries were respected.

Companionship marriage offered several advantages. It allowed emotional agency for young women and men who otherwise had little influence over formal marriage negotiations. It also served as a compatibility test, enabling young adults to assess potential marital stability and affection before entering rigid lineage-dominated unions.⁵⁰ However, the system had challenges. Husbands often viewed past companions as rivals, leading to jealousy, tensions, and occasional conflict. Elders feared that strong companionship ties could undermine the authority of arranged marriages and erode

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lineage control.⁵¹ Additionally, the requirement for companions to participate in fertility rituals sometimes caused disputes, especially if the companion refused or demanded compensation. Despite these issues, companionship remained a respected institution that complemented Tiv marriage systems rather than threatening them. Marriage by purchase developed in Tivland as trade expanded with neighboring ethnic groups such as the Jukun, Hausa, and Alago. Increased access to cattle, brass rods, imported cloth, and other valuables gradually made it possible for wealthier men to acquire wives through direct payment, bypassing the need for wards required in exchange marriage.⁵² Although Tiv society valued reciprocity over commodification, economic diversification in the precolonial period encouraged the emergence of alternative marriage pathways for men without suitable sisters or wards. This form of marriage therefore arose in response to socio-economic changes rather than traditional Tiv norms, making it less culturally esteemed.⁵³

The process of marriage by purchase involved negotiations between the groom's family and the bride's family, during which the bride's value was assessed based on her lineage status, physical health, industriousness, and fertility potential. Payment could involve cattle, goats,

brass rods, cloth, hoes, or other economic items acquired through trade.⁵⁴ Once payment was accepted, the bride was escorted to her new home, usually with minimal ritual ceremony and little involvement of extended lineage groups. The absence of elaborate rituals—especially akombo rites—was a defining feature, contributing to the perception that marriage by purchase lacked the legitimacy or spiritual depth of exchange marriage.⁵⁵ Children born from such marriages often had ambiguous lineage status unless later incorporated through additional rituals or exchanges.

Marriage by purchase offered certain benefits, particularly for men who lacked female siblings or wards necessary for exchange marriage. It also promoted upward mobility for industrious men who had acquired wealth through hunting, trading, or farming.⁵⁶ However, the practice faced significant cultural challenges. It was socially stigmatized because it commodified women, reducing the communal reciprocity valued in Tiv culture.⁵⁷ Moreover, in the event of the husband's death, the wife and her children risked being excluded from his lineage because their membership was not secured through exchange-based kinship obligations. Such children were sometimes viewed as "outsiders," creating tensions in inheritance and lineage

continuity.⁵⁸ For these reasons, marriage by purchase was practiced but not widely respected before colonial rule.

Elopement, known as *ii kwase*, emerged as a marriage system partly because of the strict control elders exercised over marital arrangements. In many cases, young lovers resorted to elopement when families disapproved of their union due to lineage conflicts, bridewealth expectations, or prior exchange obligations.⁵⁹ Oral accounts recorded by Rupert East in *Akiga's Story* show that elopement functioned as a youthful strategy to bypass parental authority when individuals felt strongly connected or when negotiation processes broke down.⁶⁰ Therefore, elopement did not arise from rebellion alone but from the inherent tension between lineage obligations and personal desire within Tiv society.

Elopement occurred when the man and woman fled secretly—often at night or after a communal event—and sought refuge in the man's compound or a distant relative's homestead. Immediately after elopement, the man's family prepared for confrontation, as the bride's relatives could arrive demanding her return or compensation.⁶¹ Negotiations typically followed, involving payments such as goats, cloth, or livestock to appease the bride's family. Elders

mediated the dispute, determining whether the union would be recognized or dissolved. In many cases, elopement eventually led to either *kem* or exchange marriage, especially if compensation restored family honor and lineage obligations.⁶² It offered several advantages, particularly for couples whose desire to marry was blocked by family politics, exchange debts, or economic hardship. It allowed young women greater agency, enabling them to choose partners based on affection rather than lineage pressure.⁶³ However, elopement also carried significant risks. It was often viewed as shameful to the woman's family and could trigger violent confrontations between lineages. Children born from elopement marriages faced legitimacy issues until formal compensation or recognition occurred. Additionally, elopement sometimes escalated into long-term disputes if families refused reconciliation, thereby destabilizing inter-lineage relations.⁶⁴ Despite these challenges, the system persisted because it provided an important counterweight to patriarchal control within precolonial Tiv society.

However, changes in warfare, migration, and economic interactions shaped the evolution of Tiv marriage. As settlements faced threats from slave raiders or disputes with neighboring

groups, marriage alliances became crucial for security. Marriages across clan or territorial lines expanded networks of mutual defense.⁶⁵ The evolution of spiritual obligations—particularly transformations in akombo rituals—also influenced marriage. Some akombo became associated with fertility and household protection, requiring proper observance during marriage negotiations. Over time, these rituals became standardized and linked to specific marriage forms.⁶⁶

Furthermore, economic diversification contributed to changes in marriage evolution. As cattle, brass rods, and woven cloths became more widely available, alternative marriage pathways emerged, reducing reliance on exchange alone. These economic shifts made marriage more dynamic and adaptable to family circumstances.⁶⁷

Polygyny increased with economic prosperity, leading to the evolution of systems that enabled men to marry multiple wives. The need to balance commitments across wives required new norms regulating jealousy, household labor, and lineage claims.⁶⁸

On the other hand, social competition and prestige became increasingly tied to marriage practices. A man's ability to fulfill exchange obligations, attract a companion, or pay

bridewealth became measures of masculine achievement. Over time, marriages became arenas for asserting social rank within the lineage system.⁶⁹ By 1914, Tiv marriage had evolved into a mature, multifaceted institution reflecting centuries of adaptation. Its complexity reveals that Tiv society possessed deep cultural sophistication long before colonial contact. Marriage was not static but dynamic, evolving through social, economic, and ritual transformations.

1.4 The Conduct of Traditional Marriage System in Tivland

Generally, the conduct of marriage in Tivland followed carefully structured stages. Courtship began through family visits, companionship relations, or interactions at communal activities. Families assessed the character of prospective spouses to ensure compatibility and lineage suitability.⁷⁰ Once interest was expressed, elders initiated discussions to determine the appropriate marriage form. Exchange marriages required early identification of wards and negotiation of equivalence, while kem marriage involved determining acceptable payments.⁷¹ In exchange marriage, family's formalized agreements by designating specific wards for exchange. Rituals were performed to bless the

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union and protect the bride from spiritual harm related to akombo.⁷²

Again, in the kem, pre-marital investigations were conducted to confirm that the bride and groom were not close kin. This step reflected the strict exogamy rules central to maintaining lineage purity and preventing incest taboos.⁷³ Negotiation involved the groom's family visiting the bride's compound with gifts such as food, tobacco, or small livestock. These gestures signaled respect and initiated formal dialogue between lineages.⁷⁴ Also, kem marriage required installment payments over time. The groom's gradual fulfillment of these obligations demonstrated commitment, and each payment conferred incremental marital rights.⁷⁵

Thereafter, wedding ceremonies involved dancing, drumming, feasting, and communal blessings. Women celebrated the bride with songs and ululations, while men performed rituals marking the groom's transition into full adulthood.⁷⁶ Upon arrival at her husband's home, the bride was placed in her mother-in-law's hut or the hut of a senior wife. She underwent days of seclusion, during which she was introduced gradually to her new domestic responsibilities.⁷⁷

Rituals such as goat slaughter or chicken sacrifice accompanied the bride's arrival. These rituals symbolized purification, protection from witchcraft, and acceptance by the lineage.⁷⁸ The bride was ceremonially smeared with camwood (ondo), marking her transition into womanhood. Her first trip to the stream with female relatives symbolized her acceptance into the household.⁷⁹ It should also be noted that marriage disputes—such as infidelity, elopement, or failure to fulfill exchange obligations—were resolved through elders who used ritual sanctions, compensation, or lineage mediation to restore harmony.⁸⁰ Once married, couples were bound by moral expectations emphasizing fidelity, cooperation in farming, and adherence to lineage norms. The lineage monitored marital conduct to protect its reputation and ensure stable family life.

1.6 Conclusion

The Tiv marriage system before 1914 represented a highly organized, culturally rich institution intricately tied to lineage structure, spirituality, and economic life. Marriage served not only as a personal union but also as a mechanism for reinforcing inter-lineage ties, expanding networks of cooperation, and ensuring social continuity. The numerous marriage forms available to Tiv families reflected

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adaptability, sophistication, and responsiveness to changing demographic and economic conditions. Rituals associated with akombo and the authority of elders maintained moral order, protected fertility, and stabilized households.

References:

Bohannan, Laura, and Paul Bohannan. *The Tiv of Central Nigeria*. (London: International African Institute, 1968), 69.

Sai Akiga, *Akiga's Story*. Translated and edited by Rupert East. (Ibadan: University Press, later editions by Caltop Publications, 1930/1939), 106.

Bohannan, Laura, and Paul Bohannan. *The Tiv of Central Nigeria*, 72

Alfred A. Torkula, *The Cultural Institutions of marriage and Family Stability among the Tiv People of Central Nigeria*, (Jos: Ehindero Press Ltd., 2004), 15-16.

Bohannan, Laura, and Paul Bohannan. *The Tiv of Central Nigeria*, 83.

Akpenpuun, Dzurgba. *On the Tiv of Central Nigeria: A Cultural Perspective*. (Ibadan: John Archers Publishers, 2007), 62.

Oral interview, Thomas Igyah, 61years, clergy, Gboko, 17/11/2025.

Alfred Akawe Torkula. *The Tiv and Their Culture*. (Makurdi: Azaron Nigeria Ltd., 2010), 71

Prior to colonial intrusion, the Tiv maintained a dynamic but deeply rooted marital system that embodied their worldview, values, and communal heritage.

Downes, R. M. *Notes on the Tribes of Northern Nigeria*. (London: Oxford University Press, 1933), 56.

Alfred A. Torkula, *The Concept, Practice, and Colonial Influence on Kinship System among The Tiv People of Central Nigeria*, (Jos: Midland Press Ltd., 2004), 17

Alfred A. Torkula, *The Concept, Practice, and Colonial Influence on Kinship System among the Tiv People of Central Nigeria*, 20-21.

Oral interview, Thomas Igyah, 2025

Bohannan, Laura, and Paul Bohannan. *The Tiv of Central Nigeria*, 57.

Akiga, Sai. *Akiga's Story*. Edited by Rupert East. (London: International African Institute, 1939), 117.

Akpenpuun, Dzurgba. *On the Tiv of Central Nigeria: A Cultural Perspective*, 106.

Alfred Akawe Torkula. *The Tiv and Their Culture*, 33.

Akiga, Sai. *Akiga's Story*. Translated and edited by Rupert East. (Ibadan: University Press, later

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- editions by Caltop Publications, 1930/1939), 106.
- East, Rupert. Akiga's Story (revised edition). (Ibadan: Ibadan University Press, 1965), 109
- Akpenpuun, Dzurgba. On the Tiv of Central Nigeria: A Cultural Perspective, 65.
- R. M. Downes. Notes on the Tribes of Northern Nigeria. (London: Oxford University Press, 1933).
- Akiga, Sai. Akiga's Story. Translated and edited by Rupert East. (Ibadan: University Press, later editions by Caltop Publications, 1930/1939), 106.
- Bohannan, Laura, and Paul Bohannan. The Tiv of Central Nigeria, 75.
- East, Rupert. Akiga's Story (revised edition), 107
- Alfred A. Torkula, the Cosmology in Tiv Worldview, (Makurdi: Oracle Business Limited, 2006), 5.
- Alfred A. Torkula, the Cultural Institutions of Marriage and Family Stability among the Tiv People of Central Nigeria, (Jos: Ehindero Press Ltd., 2004), 55.
- Captain R.M. Downes, the Tiv Tribe, (Kaduna: London: Oxford University, 1933), 16
- Bohannan, Laura, and Paul Bohannan. The Tiv of Central Nigeria. (London: International African Institute, 1968), 69
- Downes, R. M. Notes on the Tribes of Northern Nigeria, 45.
- Akpenpuun, Dzurgba. On the Tiv of Central Nigeria: A Cultural Perspective, 75
- Downes, R. M. Notes on the Tribes of Northern Nigeria, 45.
- Downes, R. M. Notes on the Tribes of Northern Nigeria, 47.
- Bohannan, Laura, and Paul Bohannan. The Tiv of Central Nigeria, 71.
- R. M. Downes. Notes on the Tribes of Northern Nigeria, 56.
- Akiga, Sai. Akiga's Story. Translated and edited by Rupert East, 123.
- Bohannan, Laura, and Paul Bohannan. The Tiv of Central Nigeria, 52.
- Alfred Akawe Torkula. The Tiv and Their Culture, 75.
- Akpenpuun, Dzurgba. On the Tiv of Central Nigeria: A Cultural Perspective, 108.
- Akiga, Sai. Akiga's Story. Translated and edited by Rupert East, 124.
- Downes, R. M. Notes on the Tribes of Northern Nigeria, 50.
- Akpenpuun, Dzurgba. On the Tiv of Central Nigeria: A Cultural Perspective, 111.

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Bohannan, Laura, and Paul Bohannan. The Tiv of Central Nigeria, 53.

Akiga, Sai. Akiga's Story. Translated and edited by Rupert East, 115.

Akpenpuun, Dzurgba. On the Tiv of Central Nigeria: A Cultural Perspective, 87.

Bohannan, Laura, and Paul Bohannan. The Tiv of Central Nigeria, 54.

Alfred Akawe Torkula. The Tiv and Their Culture, 78.

Akpenpuun, Dzurgba. On the Tiv of Central Nigeria: A Cultural Perspective, 89.

Akiga, Sai. Akiga's Story. Translated and edited by Rupert East, 154–156.

Alfred Akawe Torkula. The Tiv and Their Culture, 81.

Akiga, Sai. Akiga's Story. Edited by Rupert East, 156.

Akpenpuun, Dzurgba. On the Tiv of Central Nigeria: A Cultural Perspective, 112.

Alfred Akawe Torkula. The Tiv and Their Culture, 82.

Akiga, Sai. Akiga's Story. Edited by Rupert East, 158.

Akiga, Sai. Akiga's Story. Edited by Rupert East, 130–132.

Bohannan, Laura, and Paul Bohannan. The Tiv of Central Nigeria, 56.

Akpenpuun, Dzurgba. On the Tiv of Central Nigeria: A Cultural Perspective, 88.

Akiga, Sai. Akiga's Story. Edited by Rupert East, 133.

Alfred Akawe Torkula. The Tiv and Their Culture, 85.

Bohannan, Laura, and Paul Bohannan. The Tiv of Central Nigeria, 57.

Akpenpuun, Dzurgba. On the Tiv of Central Nigeria: A Cultural Perspective, 90.

Akpenpuun, Dzurgba. On the Tiv of Central Nigeria: A Cultural Perspective, 102.

Rupert East. Akiga's Story (editor), 147.

Akiga, Sai. Akiga's Story. Translated and edited by Rupert East, 148–149.

Akpenpuun, Dzurgba. On the Tiv of Central Nigeria: A Cultural Perspective, 103.

Alfred Akawe Torkula. The Tiv and Their Culture, 88.

Akpenpuun, Dzurgba. On the Tiv of Central Nigeria: A Cultural Perspective, 104.

Alfred Akawe Torkula. The Tiv and Their Culture, 76.

Akiga, Sai. Akiga's Story. Translated and edited by Rupert East, 106.

Bohannan, Laura, and Paul Bohannan. The Tiv of Central Nigeria, 96.

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Akpenpuun, Dzurgba. On the Tiv of Central Nigeria:
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Bohannan, Laura, and Paul Bohannan. The Tiv of
Central Nigeria, 73.

East, Rupert. Akiga's Story (revised edition), 55.

Downes, R. M. Notes on the Tribes of Northern
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Akiga, Sai. Akiga's Story. Translated and edited by
Rupert East, 72.

Akpenpuun, Dzurgba. On the Tiv of Central Nigeria:
A Cultural Perspective, 113.

Bohannan, Laura, and Paul Bohannan. The Tiv of
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Akiga, Sai. Akiga's Story. Translated and edited by
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Akpenpuun, Dzurgba. On the Tiv of Central Nigeria:
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Downes, R. M. Notes on the Tribes of Northern
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Laura Bohannan and Paul Bohannan. The Tiv of
Central Nigeria, 107.

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